

ROSES

Software Funding Opportunities

F.7 Support for Open-Source Tools, Frameworks, and Libraries

F.14 High Priority Open-Source Science

F.8 Supplements for Open-Source Science

F.3 Exoplanets Research

F.5 Future Investigators in NASA Earth and Space Science and Technology

F.6 Science Activation Program

A.15 Modeling, Analysis, and Prediction

A.41 SERVIR Applied Sciences Team

A.43 Earth Action: Health and Air Quality

B.20 Heliophysics Tools and Methods

... and more! Note that some programs (e.g. most astrophysics ROSES elements) may fund software but proposals are in competition with research proposals.

What Open Software Will NASA Fund?

§ No due date program: proposals accepted any time.

* Proposer should have an existing ROSES award or be from a NASA facility/center (e.g. JPL, APL).

What Domain-Specific Software Will NASA Fund?

NSPIRES

<https://nspires.nasaprs.com/>

§ No due date program: proposals accepted any time.